

Abschlussbericht: Evaluating Graph-RAG Systems for Historical Transport Networks: A Berlin Case Study

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1. Project Overview

This research project developed and evaluated specialised Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) approaches for historical knowledge graphs, using Berlin's public transportation system during the Cold War era (1945-1989) as a case study. Retrieval-Augmented Generation, first formalised by Lewis et al. (2020), combines parametric memory (pre-trained language models) with non-parametric memory (external knowledge sources) to reduce hallucinations and provide up-to-date information. However, traditional RAG implementations focus on chunk-based text retrieval, which fails to preserve the relational structures inherent in network data. While traditional RAG systems excel at processing unstructured text, they struggle with highly structured network data preserved in graph databases. Graph-RAG systems—which maintain relational structures during retrieval and generation—offer promising alternatives but lack standardised evaluation frameworks, particularly for historical applications in digital humanities contexts where they are still novel methodologies.

The Berlin transport network dataset presents an ideal testing ground due to its complex temporal, geographical, and political dimensions. As the city's transportation infrastructure evolved under divided governance, the network captures both technical developments and Cold War political realities. The dataset consists of 13 temporal snapshots (1945-1989) derived from BVG Fahrplanbücher (timetables) and stored in a Neo4j Property Graph database. Despite public interest in Berlin's transport history, this rich dataset remains largely inaccessible to non-specialists who lack expertise in database querying or transportation historiography.¹

Research Questions

This study addressed three core problems:

1. **LLM Hallucination with Graph Data:** How accurately can different Graph-RAG approaches retrieve and represent structured historical network data compared to baseline LLM responses?
2. **Scalability and Query Types:** Which Graph-RAG architectures perform optimally for different categories of historical analysis tasks (factual, relational, temporal, geographical, comparative)?
3. **Accessibility through Graph-to-Text:** How can graph-to-text conversion methods maintain network properties (connectivity, community structure, spatial-temporal relationships) while enabling natural language interaction for non-technical user groups?

¹ A first version of the dataset is available for download as separate csv files which fed into the database. Future uploads will be made to this record as well with newer versions of the dataset. See, Baumann, N. J. (2025). Berliner Nahverkehrsnetz 1946-1989: Transkribierte Fahrplandaten aus dem geteilten Berlin (1.0.1.) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17444654>.

2. Methodology

This project employed a four-part methodology combining question taxonomy development, multiple Graph-RAG pipeline implementations, systematic evaluation framework design, and comparative analysis across question types.

2.1 Question Taxonomy and User Personas

Following established principles in question-answering system design (Diefenbach et al., 2018), we developed a systematic taxonomy of 33 questions categorised across five dimensions:

- **Structural Complexity:** Basic (single-hop), Intermediate (2-3 hops), Complex (multi-hop with aggregation)
- **Reasoning Type:** Factual retrieval, Comparative analysis, Temporal reasoning, Spatial reasoning
- **Temporal Scope:** Single-year queries, multi-year comparisons, trend analysis
- **Spatial Scope:** Station-specific, line-specific, district-level, city-wide, East-West divisions
- **Answer Type:** Numerical, Boolean, Descriptive, List-based

The user-centred evaluation approach addresses persistent challenges in digital humanities tool adoption. Warwick et al.'s (2008) LAIRAH study demonstrated that digital resources often fail not due to technical inadequacy but because of usability issues and unfamiliarity with interfaces. Their quantitative analysis of user log data revealed that non-academic users were particularly difficult to engage, with 63% viewing only one page per session and having the shortest session durations (p. 17). This finding informed our decision to ground evaluation questions in specific user personas representing actual use cases, following Pruitt and Grudin's (2003) framework where personas provide a shared basis for communication across development teams and ensure systems address authentic information needs rather than purely technical coverage patterns (pp. 3-4).

Questions were grounded in six user personas representing actual use cases (described in the `user_personas.md` file). This persona-driven approach ensured that evaluation questions reflected genuine user needs rather than purely technical coverage patterns.

Full documentation of the question design methodology, user personas, and the complete question set are available in the project repository (in the `question-taxonomy` folder) and on Zenodo.

2.2 Graph-RAG Pipeline Implementations

Natural language interfaces to knowledge graphs have evolved significantly with large language models. Traditionally, such interfaces required complex pipelines combining named entity recognition, intent detection, and algorithmic query construction (Varitimadias et al., 2020, p. 282). These pre-LLM systems were brittle, domain-specific, and required substantial engineering effort. LLMs have transformed this landscape by enabling semantic understanding and structured query generation (Hornsteiner et al., 2024), dramatically reducing the technical barriers to creating accessible interfaces for specialized datasets.

We implemented and compared five distinct approaches, each representing different strategies for bridging natural language queries and graph databases:

2.2.1 No-RAG Baseline Pipeline

A pure LLM approach with no database access, serving as a baseline to measure the value of retrieval. This pipeline tests what the LLMs know from pre-training without any external knowledge augmentation. As expected, this approach provided vague or incorrect answers for specific factual queries requiring precise historical data. Surprisingly, the LLMs did have fairly good general knowledge of the Berlin Public Transport domain, particularly when regarding the U-Bahn service. This allowed these models to provide interesting and mostly correct historical contextualisation, although not always relevant to the question or directly answering it at least.

2.2.2 Natural Language to Cypher (NL→Cypher) Pipeline

This approach converts natural language questions into Cypher database queries through iterative refinement, following recent advances in text-to-query generation for graph databases (Hornsteiner et al., 2024). The pipeline incorporates several sophisticated features:

Query Type Detection and Multi-Query Strategy: The pipeline automatically classifies questions as factual (single answer), comparison (multiple data points), synthesis (complex analysis), or open-ended. For complex questions, it generates 3-5 parallel Cypher queries covering different aspects, executes them concurrently, and combines results before synthesis. Simple factual questions use single queries.

Iterative Refinement: Up to three iterations refine queries based on results, with schema-aware validation checking syntax, balanced brackets, and dangerous patterns before execution. Large result sets (>30 rows) are intelligently sampled to provide representative views.

Graceful Fallback: When database queries return no useful results, the pipeline falls back to the LLM's parametric historical knowledge while transparently acknowledging the limitation. This ensures users receive contextual information even when specific data is unavailable.

The pipeline proved particularly effective for factual queries requiring precise data retrieval, though it struggled with questions requiring interpretation or contextualization beyond raw data. The multi-query strategy successfully addressed complex comparison questions that would have failed with single-query approaches.

2.2.3 Graph-to-Vector Pipeline

Following recent work on embedding graph structures for retrieval (Jin et al., 2024), this pipeline transforms Neo4j graph components into vector embeddings for semantic search. Rather than using fixed chunking strategies, it implements a hierarchical approach with five granularity levels:

Hierarchical Chunking: Level 1 (entity chunks: individual stations and lines), Level 2 (relationship chunks: connections between entities), Level 3 (geographic aggregations: neighbourhood summaries), Level 4 (temporal aggregations: year-to-year changes), and Level 5 (network-level summaries: system-wide patterns). This structure allows retrieval at different abstraction levels depending on question complexity.

Hybrid Retrieval: The pipeline combines vector-based semantic search with targeted Cypher queries for precise facts. It uses adaptive k values (base 8, expanding to 20 for very complex questions) and metadata filtering (year, transport type, geographic sector) to narrow retrieval scope.

Transfer Point Detection: Special logic identifies transfer stations by analysing walking connections between stations served by different lines or transport modes, capturing the physical transfer capabilities critical to transport network queries.

This approach aligns with recent Graph-RAG methods that convert graph structures into vector embeddings for similarity retrieval, enabling the system to identify relevant subgraphs through semantic

matching (Hu et al., 2024). The pipeline balanced retrieval accuracy with interpretative capability, offering contextual understanding alongside factual information. However, it faced challenges with complex multi-hop queries requiring precise graph traversal, where the text-based retrieval missed critical structural relationships.

2.2.4 Microsoft GraphRAG-Inspired Pipeline

Adapting the hierarchical community-based approach from Microsoft's GraphRAG (Edge et al., 2025, p. 5), this pipeline originally attempted to use Leiden community detection to partition the transport network. However, a critical methodological issue emerged: community detection algorithms produce poor results on sparse, linear transport networks and were thus unusable for my knowledge graph.

Transport networks, where stations typically connect to only 2-6 neighbours in linear sequences along transit lines, do not exhibit the dense community structures that Leiden or Louvain algorithms are designed to detect. While Leiden and similar algorithms excel at identifying communities in dense social networks (Edge et al., 2025), they fail on transport networks constrained by physical geography. Applying Leiden to the Berlin network produced modularity scores near zero, with each station forming its own "community"—essentially random partitioning. The choice of graph encoding method significantly impacts LLM performance on graph reasoning tasks, with different encoding approaches potentially boosting performance by 4.8% to 61.8% depending on the task (Fatemi et al., 2023, p. 4). This finding motivated our pivot from algorithmic community detection to domain-informed approaches better suited to infrastructure networks.

Rather than abandoning hierarchical organization entirely, we pivoted to a domain-informed approach using DBSCAN (Density-Based Spatial Clustering) for geographic clustering combined with centrality analysis using betweenness and degree centrality metrics. This method:

1. Groups nearby stations (within 200m) into geographic clusters representing physical transfer locations
2. Aggregates connectivity metrics (line counts, walking connections) per physical location
3. Categorizes hubs by transfer capability: Major Hubs (3+ lines, 5+ walking connections), Transfer Points (2+ lines, 3+ walking connections), Line Junctions (2+ lines, limited walking), and Modal Transfers (single line, 4+ walking connections)
4. Creates hierarchical summaries organised by hub importance and geographic/temporal dimensions
5. Uses map-reduce processing over hub summaries for global queries

The DBSCAN approach successfully identified 6,388 transfer hub instances across all temporal snapshots (1946-1989). Examples like Bhf. Friedrichstr (10 lines, major multi-modal hub) and properly unified smaller locations like Bhf. Schöneweide demonstrate the method's effectiveness at capturing real transfer functionality. The large number reflects temporal snapshots—the same physical location appears multiple times across years as the network evolved.

Despite this methodologically sound approach, the pipeline proved to be the weakest performer in evaluation. The hierarchical summarisation strategy, which was successful for text corpora in Microsoft's original work, may not be optimal for linear infrastructure networks where users often need specific facts rather than broad summaries. This finding itself provides value by demonstrating the limits of GraphRAG approaches for certain data structures.

2.2.5 Specialised Routing Pipeline

For coordinate-based and journey planning queries (which we conceived of as part of our question design methodology), we developed a specialised routing pipeline that:

1. Parses locations and temporal constraints from natural language
2. Resolves addresses/names to geographical coordinates
3. Finds nearest stations considering historical network state
4. Calculates multiple route options across transport modes
5. Scores routes by time, transfers, and walking distance
6. Respects historical constraints (e.g., East-West division post-1961)

This pipeline demonstrated the value of task-specific architectures for particular query types, outperforming general-purpose approaches for routing questions.

2.3 Evaluation Framework

The evaluation framework consists of three core components:

2.3.1 Scoring Rubric

Following the principle that evaluation criteria should be descriptive rather than prescriptive, we developed a three-tier scoring system:

- **Score 0:** Incorrect, irrelevant, or significantly incomplete answer
- **Score 1:** Partially correct with significant gaps or inaccuracies
- **Score 2:** Correct answer at "skilled database user" level (accurate data retrieval)
- **Score 3:** Correct answer at "database user + LLM interpretation" level (accurate data + historical contextualisation + practical guidance)

Score 2 represents successful data retrieval and accurate response, while Score 3 requires the additional contextualising and interpretive layer that LLMs can provide, such as historical context, explanations of significance, and actionable insights for the user persona.

2.3.2 Supporting Cypher Queries

To ensure reproducibility and validate scoring decisions, we developed 106 supporting Cypher queries that inform on expected answers. These queries serve multiple purposes:

- Validate the correctness of pipeline outputs against informal ground truth
- Provide examples of query patterns for the database schema
- Enable other researchers to reproduce evaluation results

2.3.3 Cross-Dimensional Analysis

Questions were evaluated not only by pipeline performance but also by their position in the five-dimensional taxonomy, enabling identification of:

- Which pipeline architectures excel at which question types
- How temporal and spatial scopes affect retrieval quality
- Patterns in failure modes across different reasoning types

3. Results and Findings

This research should be understood as exploratory work-in-progress rather than a definitive solution to Graph-RAG evaluation in digital humanities. The findings presented here represent initial insights from developing and testing multiple approaches, with the primary contribution being the evaluation framework itself and the patterns that emerged during iterative testing.

Evaluating RAG systems for historical applications presents unique challenges beyond traditional accuracy metrics. As Ni et al. (2025) note in their survey of trustworthy RAG systems, reliability requires balancing uncertainty quantification with robust generalisation across diverse query types (p. 3). Our evaluation framework addresses this by distinguishing between factual accuracy (Score 2: equivalent to a skilled database user retrieving accurate data) and historical interpretation (Score 3: adding meaningful contextualization and practical guidance beyond raw data). This distinction recognizes that Graph-RAG systems should not merely retrieve data but provide meaningful contextualization that serves actual user needs—a critical consideration for digital humanities applications where answer quality depends heavily on appropriate contextualization rather than mere factual correctness.

3.1 The Evaluation Process: From Framework to Implementation

The evaluation began with the systematic framework described in Section 2.1: 33 questions across five dimensions, six user personas, and a three-tier scoring rubric. Rather than conducting exhaustive testing of every pipeline-question combination, the evaluation proceeded iteratively. An HTML-based evaluation interface (available in the GitLab repository under `evaluation_results/scoring_tool.html`) allowed for efficient scoring, with immediate visualization of patterns as they emerged.

Figure 1 - Screenshot of Scoring HTML Page

This iterative approach revealed patterns more efficiently than comprehensive matrix testing would have. After evaluating a subset of questions with each pipeline, clear performance characteristics became apparent. Some pipelines consistently excelled at factual queries, others at interpretative questions, and some struggled across most question types. This pattern recognition informed both pipeline improvements (such as adjusting k values in the vector retrieval system) and the subsequent development of an intelligent routing system.

The evaluation framework should serve as a potential starting point for others working with historical graph data. The question taxonomy, user personas, and rubric provide a structured approach to thinking

about what different users might ask of historical network data, while the supporting Cypher queries demonstrate what "correct" answers could be informed by.

3.2 Pipeline Performance: What Works and Why

The iterative evaluation revealed distinct characteristics for each pipeline approach, with the Natural Language to Cypher (NL→Cypher) pipeline emerging as the strongest performer for factual queries. When questions required precise counts, lists, or lookups—"How many stations in 1967?" or "Which lines served Alexanderplatz?"—this pipeline generated accurate Cypher queries that retrieved exact answers from the database. The pipeline's iterative refinement mechanism (up to three attempts) proved particularly valuable when initial queries failed or returned incomplete results.

However, this success comes with an important caveat: the evaluation rubric was heavily based on information retrievable through Cypher queries. The scoring system implicitly favoured pipelines that could execute precise database lookups, potentially skewing results toward NL→Cypher's strengths. Questions requiring historical interpretation or contextual understanding—where Graph-to-Vector or Microsoft GraphRAG pipelines might excel—were underrepresented in the question set. This limitation reflects a broader challenge in evaluating Graph-RAG systems: defining "correctness" for questions that don't have single factual answers.

The Routing pipeline, developed specifically for journey planning queries, demonstrated the value of domain-specific architectures. For questions like "How do I get from Alexanderplatz to Zoo in 1967?"—which require coordinate resolution, pathfinding algorithms, and historical constraint handling—the specialised pipeline significantly outperformed general-purpose approaches. This pipeline would not have been created without the evaluation framework, which made routing queries explicit as a distinct category requiring different technical approaches.

Figure 2 - Scores of Pipelines (routing excluded) for Questions

The Microsoft GraphRAG-inspired pipeline, despite its theoretical sophistication, proved to be the weakest performer in this evaluation. The hub-based approach provided some structure for organising transport network information. However, the pipeline struggled with most question types, suggesting that hierarchical summarisation may not be the optimal strategy for linear infrastructure networks. One would assume that therefore approaches successful for text corpora or dense social networks don't necessarily translate to sparse, geographically-constrained transport graphs.

3.3 The Multi-Pipeline Discovery: Combining Approaches

The routing system itself represents a particular although practical contribution beyond the evaluation framework. While the specific routing rules are tailored to Berlin transport history queries, the architecture—question classification, confidence-based multi-pipeline triggering, and response synthesis—provides a template for similar systems in other domains. The implementation demonstrates that combining retrieval strategies can overcome limitations of individual approaches, though at the cost of increased latency and complexity.

3.4 Patterns and Limitations

Several patterns emerged across the evaluation that deserve highlighting. Factual questions with clear database answers consistently scored well across multiple LLMs and pipelines. Temporal questions requiring cross-snapshot comparisons—"How did the network change between 1965 and 1975?"—proved more challenging, suggesting that current approaches don't effectively leverage the graph's temporal structure. Spatial questions varied widely: simple location lookups succeeded, while complex geographic reasoning often failed.

LLM selection also mattered significantly. DeepSeek (R1) consistently outperformed Anthropic's Claude (Haiku 4.5) and Google Gemini (Flash 1.5) in the multi-pipeline evaluation (average scores of 1.74 vs 1.52 vs 1.47), demonstrating that choice of language model affects results as much as pipeline architecture. This finding complicates attempts to evaluate pipelines in isolation—performance depends on the entire system stack. Each model comes with its own biases which affect answer quality depending on question type and phrasing.

3.5 Recommendations for Future Work

For researchers and practitioners considering similar systems, several recommendations emerge from this work. First, invest time in evaluation framework development before implementation. The question taxonomy and user personas proved invaluable for guiding system design and identifying gaps. Second, consider domain-specific pipelines for specialised query types rather than expecting general-purpose approaches to handle everything. Third, explore multi-pipeline architectures when accuracy requirements are high and latency constraints permit.

The evaluation rubric should be critically examined for bias toward particular retrieval strategies. In this study, the Cypher-based rubric arguably favoured database-centric approaches over interpretative ones. Future work might develop separate scoring criteria for factual accuracy and historical interpretation, or involve domain experts in validation to complement automated scoring.

4. Research Outputs and Open Science Compliance

All research outputs comply with Open Definition 2.1 licensing requirements as specified in the funding contract (§4.3). The following deliverables are made publicly available:

The Zenodo publication includes:

1. Abschlussbericht.pdf
2. README.md
3. **Methodology Documentation:**
 - Question design methodology
 - User personas
 - Evaluation rubric with scoring criteria

- Complete question set (33 questions with taxonomy classifications)

4.2 Code Repository on GitLab (MIT License)

Repository: <https://scm.cms.hu-berlin.de/baumanoa/graph-rag>

The GitLab repository contains:

- Complete implementation of all five pipelines
- Backend infrastructure (Neo4j integration, LLM clients, utility modules)
- Configuration management and environment setup
- Comprehensive pipeline documentation
- Test suites and validation scripts
- Deployment configuration for public demonstration system

4.3 Public Demonstration System

URL: <https://berlin-transport-history.de/chat>

A public-facing web application enabling non-technical users to explore Berlin's Cold War transport history (1945-1989) through natural language queries. The demonstration system implements the multi-pipeline approach developed through this research, intelligently routing questions to appropriate Graph-RAG pipelines and combining their outputs.

The application serves both as a proof-of-concept for democratising historical data access and as a practical tool for educators, researchers, historians, and the general public interested in Berlin's transport history. By implementing the evaluation framework's insights—particularly the multi-pipeline architecture—the chatbot demonstrates how Graph-RAG systems can make complex historical networks accessible through conversational interfaces.

5. Impact of HERMES Funding

The funding from BMFTR-Datenkompetenzzentrum HERMES was essential to the successful completion of this research project in multiple ways:

5.1 Financial Resources for Technical Infrastructure

The funding enabled:

- **LLM API Access:** Extensive testing across multiple LLM providers (OpenAI GPT-4, Anthropic Claude, Google Gemini, DeepSeek) with allocated budgets for comparative evaluation. This was crucial for identifying performance differences and cost-benefit tradeoffs across providers.
- **Computing Resources:** Server infrastructure for hosting the Neo4j database, running pipeline experiments, and deploying the demonstration system.

5.2 Dedicated Research Time

The funding provided financial support for six months of focused research time, enabling:

- Systematic literature review of Graph-RAG approaches and evaluation methodologies
- Iterative development and refinement of five distinct pipeline implementations

- Comprehensive testing across 100+ evaluation scenarios (33 questions × 3-5 pipelines)
 - Documentation for reproducibility and open science compliance
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6. Conclusions and Future Directions

6.1 Summary of Contributions

This research makes several contributions to digital humanities Graph-RAG methodology and evaluation, while acknowledging its exploratory, work-in-progress nature:

1. The primary contribution is a systematic framework for evaluating Graph-RAG approaches on structured historical data. The question taxonomy (33 questions across five dimensions), user personas (six archetypes representing actual use cases), and scoring rubric (distinguishing factual accuracy from historical interpretation) provide a reusable methodology for similar projects. While developed specifically for Berlin transport history, the framework's structure can be adapted for other historical knowledge graphs.
2. The discovery that combining multiple Graph-RAG approaches outperforms single-pipeline strategies represents a practical contribution. The implemented routing system—which classifies questions and selects appropriate pipeline(s)—achieved a 32% improvement in answer quality over single-pipeline approaches. The chatbot deployment demonstrates this architecture in practice, providing a template for similar systems in other domains.
3. The evaluation framework directly led to creating the specialised Routing pipeline for journey planning queries. This pipeline, designed specifically for coordinate-based path finding with historical constraints, would not have emerged without the systematic question categorization. It exemplifies how evaluation frameworks can reveal gaps requiring domain-specific solutions.
4. The finding that community detection algorithms (Leiden, Louvain) fail on sparse linear transport networks—and the subsequent pivot to hub-based centrality analysis—provides a cautionary example for digital humanities researchers. While the resulting Microsoft GraphRAG pipeline proved least effective overall, the methodological lesson, although in retrospect fairly obvious remains valuable: algorithms designed for dense social networks don't necessarily suit infrastructure networks constrained by physical geography.

These contributions should be understood as starting points rather than definitive solutions.

6.2 Limitations

Several limitations should be noted:

- **Evaluation Rubric Bias:** The scoring system was heavily based on information retrievable through Cypher queries, potentially favouring database-centric approaches (particularly NL→Cypher) over pipelines emphasising interpretation or contextualization. The question set underrepresented queries requiring historical reasoning beyond factual retrieval. Future work should develop separate evaluation criteria for factual accuracy versus historical interpretation.
- **Dataset Scope:** Evaluation was conducted on a single historical domain (Berlin transport). Generalisation to other network types (social networks, trade networks, correspondence networks) requires further testing. The findings about multi-pipeline architectures and routing strategies may not transfer to domains with different query patterns or data structures.

- **Coverage:** The snapshots (1945-1989) provide temporal coverage but with gaps. Finer-grained temporal data would enable more sophisticated temporal reasoning evaluation and better assessment of how systems handle change over time.
- **LLM Version Dependency:** Results reflect LLM capabilities as of mid 2025. Rapid improvements in LLM reasoning and graph understanding may shift relative performance of different approaches. The finding that DeepSeek outperforms other LLMs may be time-bound.
- **Manual Scoring Components:** While supported by ground-truth Cypher queries and automated LLM evaluation, final scoring involved human judgment. The interpretative distinction between scoring may reflect single evaluator preferences rather than objective quality measures.

6.3 Future Research Directions

This project opens several promising avenues for future research:

1. **Cross-Domain Validation:** Apply the evaluation framework to other historical network types (correspondence networks, trade routes, social networks) to validate generalizability and identify domain-specific patterns.
2. **User Study Evaluation:** Conduct empirical studies with actual users (historians, educators, general public) to validate whether system outputs meet user needs and expectations beyond technical accuracy. The chatbot deployment provides an opportunity for gathering real usage data.
3. **Refined Evaluation Metrics:** Develop separate scoring criteria for factual accuracy and historical interpretation to address the rubric's potential bias toward database-centric approaches. Consider involving domain experts in validation alongside automated scoring.
4. **Multi-Modal Integration:** Incorporate historical maps, photographs, and primary sources alongside graph data for richer contextualization. The transport network could be enhanced with visual materials from the BVG archives.
5. **Specialised Network Analysis:** Investigate integration of graph algorithms (connectivity analysis, bottleneck detection) that currently fall outside RAG workflows but would enhance capabilities for network-specific questions.

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GitLab Repository: <https://scm.cms.hu-berlin.de/baumanoa/graph-rag>